

CHALLENGES OF ELEMENTARY PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS OF THE SELECTED TEACHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN SAN PABLO CITY AMIDST THE PANDEMIC: A BASIS FOR AN ENHANCEMENT PLAN

Marionne Coronado Abac

Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng San Pablo, San Pablo City Laguna, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10892902>

ABSTRACT

The shift to the new normal in education offers educators a significant opportunity to reinvent the future. Pre-service teachers are impacted by the pandemic's chaos. This study aims to determine the challenges experienced by elementary pre-service teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study employed a phenomenological research approach, which comprised conducting virtual interviews and focus group discussions (FGD) with 15 participants from selected tertiary education institutions in the City of San Pablo. Based on the findings of this study, elementary pre-service teachers need to master the needs of teaching, a flexible style of understanding and principles, as well as the consequences of their experiences and tales as a part of the creation of their identities. The participants felt unprepared for the new phenomenon in education, but according to their experiences, they were able to utilize their potential by adapting to technology. The internet played a significant influence in the pre-service teachers' practicum, among other things that were discovered to affect their distance practice teaching. As a result, the researcher proposed an enhancement plan for student internship.

Keywords: *Challenges of Pre-service Teachers, Triangulation Method, Thematic Analysis, Internet Connection Fuels the New Set-up, Lack of Interaction*

INTRODUCTION

Amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, the pre-service teacher conducted their student teaching virtually due to the restrictions whereas there is a transition from traditional face-to-face to virtual. The usual practices of pre-service teachers are different apart from the new normal setup and force schools into a flow of learning that is full of complexities and limitations (Rasmitadila, et al., 2020). Furthermore, pre-service teachers mentioned that they mainly faced problems such as the lack of time exposure for live courses regarding the implementation; failure to establish communication with friends regarding the students; absence of internet connectivity regarding impossibility, sound problems regarding technical issues, and lack of communication regarding for the instructors (Ozudogru,2021).

As cited by, (Ozmantar & Agac, 2021), the pre-service teachers also experienced adaptational gaps in the new normal of practice teaching because they already expected that they would have face-to-face practice teaching. This means that the preparation did not jibe with the new normal of practice teaching. Furthermore, it was found that pre-service teachers in one of the state universities in the Philippines struggled with lesson planning, classroom management, and the use of technology in their demonstration teaching.

In addition, according to (Dawson & Shand, 2019), mentorship aids pre-service teachers in overcoming the challenges they face in light of the pressures they face. She emphasized that mentor assistance helps pre-service teachers feel more confident and less isolated in their jobs. Pre-service teachers need to adapt instructional approaches based on the online modality because it is likely their students might face pandemic-similar situations or a plethora of academic and non-academic challenges in the future (Hill J., 2021).

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the Challenges of Elementary Pre-service Teachers Amidst the Pandemic in the Academic Year 2021-2022.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the challenges of being elementary pre-service teachers?
2. What are the disadvantages and advantages of distance practice teaching?
3. How did the elementary pre-service teachers overcome the challenges during their practice teaching?
4. What are the strategies of pre-service used to overcome these challenges?
5. What is the recommended teaching enhancement plan for an internship?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed the phenomenological approach and experiential learning theory of Kolb. The participants of the study are elementary pre-service teachers who undergo their practice teaching program in the academic year 2021-2022 and are enrolled in the Bachelor of Elementary Education, which is randomly selected. Furthermore, the instrument used by the researcher is a researcher-made interview guide question that undergoes content validation from experts to get rid of loopholes and data biases. In collecting the data, the researcher gave a consent form to the participant and conducted a short briefing. Then, a summary of the collected data was carefully encoded and transcribed using NVivo, which was checked by a credible specialist. The triangulation method was applied in the process of the study, as was a thematic analysis after the data gathering.

RESULTS

The findings of this study are that elementary pre-service teachers need to master the needs of teaching, a flexible style of understanding and principles, as well as the consequences of their experiences and tales as a part of the creation of their identities. The participants felt unprepared for the new phenomenon in education, but according to their experiences, they were able to utilize their potential by adapting to technology. The internet played a significant role in the pre-service teachers' practicum, among other things that were discovered to affect their distance practice teaching.

DISCUSSION

A. Experiences of Elementary Pre-service Teachers Amidst the COVID-19 Pandemic

First Theme: Struggles in Practice Teaching. As the pandemic affected their internship, they had been constrained by their actual practice to their own pace, leading them to unexperienced and exposing them to unexpected learning and teaching environment which is a virtual class. The pandemic's pre-service teachers claimed that something was missing from their service to the partner school. (Ersin, Atay, & Mede, 2020). Pre-service teachers struggle in their preparation of their journey as professional teachers:

Second Theme: Unpreparedness of Pre-service Teachers. In 2020, pre-service teachers experienced the distance practice teaching. Different learning modalities used as well in the basic and tertiary education. During the utilization of online learning different universities and schools' researchers mentioned some disadvantages (Niemi & Kousi, 2020). The sudden change of learning environment has become one of the most

prevalent reasons why students are unprepared. (Giani & Martin, 2021). The participants have academic reservations regarding their readiness to teach as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Third Theme: Adapting to Technologies. The pandemic was initially perceived as a threat, but as people learned to live with it, they began to see it as a chance to advance technology and provide the globe access to opportunities that had been lost because of the pandemic. As a result, the pandemic forced educators and students to adopt new technology and make the most of their experiences and skills under the new normal. (Secundo, et al., 2021). The participants in the current study choose to embrace the new normal in their midst because they feel that this is the best way to adjust to it.

B. Factors Affecting the Experiences of Elementary Pre-service Teachers Amidst the COVID-19 Pandemic

The participants' recounted experiences during their distance student teaching paved the way for the identification of the following factors that influenced their experiences: the internet connection fuels the new set-up of education, lack of interaction, and the need for on-site set-up.

First Theme: Internet Connection Fuels the New Set-up of Education. The participants in the current study asserted that the internet has saved them from this pandemic. Despite the stress of having to use the internet for their education, they must obtain a reliable internet connection. According to the study of reference, as teachers appear to be absent in this pandemic, kids are mostly dependent on the internet. The informants went on to say that Google appears to be their mentor during the pandemic. The pre-service teachers in the current study experienced comparable issues with the reference informants (Pastores et al.,2021)

Second Theme: Lack of Interaction. The reference study made clear how crucial connections are for pre-service teachers to support and collaborate on their academic and practical journeys. Experiential learning greatly benefits from social interaction. The pre-service teachers connected online through various platforms, and through that connection, they could share knowledge, and that was essential to their student teaching experience. (Ersin & Atay, 2021)

Third Theme: The Needs of On-site Set-up. The practice teachers had to set up their classrooms in the convenience of their own homes. To give their tutees or pupils the impression that they are actually in a classroom, the classroom must have a proper setup. Even in the circumstances they are in, pre-service teachers must ensure that the learning environment is favorable. (Napanoy, Gayagay, & Tuazon, 2021). On-site set-up is necessary for teaching in the new standard of education.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the experiences of the pre-service teachers who are doing their pre-service teaching in the new normal of teaching:

1. The pre-service teachers encountered a variety of difficulties while completing their distance learning practicum, but they must adjust to the new teaching and learning modes to reach their full potential.
2. Remote practice instruction has both advantages and disadvantages. The advantages of using technology in the classroom and having a flexible schedule were mentioned by the informants, while the disadvantages included a lack of social interaction, slow internet connectivity, and the requirement for the traditional setup. For them, face-to-face instruction is unusual and the most effective way to learn.
3. Pre-service teachers used different teaching strategies and styles with the help and supervision of their cooperating teachers.
4. The researcher developed an enhancement of the teaching internship plan that may serve as a basis for the Tertiary Education Institutions and Partner Schools.'

Recommendations

The following recommendations are suggested by the researchers based on the findings of the study:

1. For the Supervising Instructors, the Student Teaching Internship Manual shall be updated or modified to improve its value and effectiveness for the preparation of pre-service teachers.
2. For the School Administrators, support the plans of the supervising instructors to ensure the quality and effectiveness of the implementation of the revised Student Teaching Internship Manual.
3. For the Partner School, collaborate with Teacher Education Institutions to produce excellent, efficient, and multi-skilled future educators.
4. For the Practice Teachers, be adaptive, flexible, reinvent, and expose themselves in different learning experiences so that they can survive in different challenges in the field of education.
5. For the Parents, motivate and support their children financially, physically, morally, and emotionally for future endeavors.
6. Future Researchers may attempt to research the same topic with different locale and more participating school.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher of the study gets the approval of the University President, the Vice President for Research and Innovation, and the data privacy officer before informed consent is obtained to carry out the study. It was forwarded to the university president and

directress of the participating schools. This has been discussed and sent to the participants after the interview. All data is treated with the utmost confidentiality.

Acknowledgments

It is with deep appreciation that I acknowledge the following for the realization of this study.

To the participants from Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng San Pablo, Canossa College – San Pablo City Inc., and Laguna State Polytechnic University – San Pablo Campus, for their time and willingness to participate in this study.

To the University President of Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng San Pablo, Dr. Sigfredo C. Adajar, University President of Laguna State Polytechnic University – San Pablo Campus, Dr. Mario R. Briones, School Directress of Canossa College – San Pablo City Inc., Sr. Lina L. Amante, FDDC, the Vice President for Research Innovations, Prof. Kristin Anne C. Corcega, the Data Privacy Officer, Dr. John Mathew Aquino, and the Administrators of PLSP, for allowing me to conduct this study and extended their help in this endeavor.

To the Vice President of Academic Affairs and Dean of the College of Teacher Education, Prof. Lorena E. Bautista, LPT, MAEng, for allowing me to use the PLSP Student Teaching Internship Manual as my basis for an enhancement plan.

To our PLSP-Graduate School Dean and my Adviser, Dr. Preciosa D. Villacruel, and the Thesis Panel Members, Dr. Elmer C. Escala, Dr. Donny Aris C. Malvar, and Dr. Sigfredo C. Adajar, for the mentorship and guardian throughout the whole study.

To my parents, relatives, friends, teachers, and classmates for the advice and encouragement to finish this study.

And Above All to the ever-loving and generous **GOD**, for gracing us life with wonderful people and challenging yet inspiring professions. Thank you, **GOD!**

REFERENCES

- Dawson, V., & Shand, J. (2019). Impact of support for pre-service teachers places in disadvantaged schools. *Issues in Educational Research*, 29(1), pp. 19 – 37. <http://www.iier.org.au/iier29/dawson.pdf>.
- Ersin, P., Atay, D., & Mede, E. (2020). “Boosting pre-service teachers’ competence and online teaching readiness through e practicum during the COVID-19 outbreak”. *International Journal of TESOL Studies*, Vol. 2 No. 2, 112-124
- Giani, M. S., & Martin, A. (2021). Mobilizing Developmental Education: The Causal Effect of Mobile App Courseware on the College Outcomes of Developmental Education Students. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*.
- Hill, J. B. (2021). Pre-service teacher experiences during COVID-19: Exploring the uncertainties between clinical practice and distance learning. *Journal of Practical Studies in Education*, 2(2), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.46809/jpse.v2i2.18>.
- Napanoy, J., Gayagay, G., & Tuazon, J. (2021). Difficulties Encountered by Pre-service Teachers: Basis of a Pre-service Training Program. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 9(2), 342-349.

- Niemi, H. M., & Kousi, P. (2020). A Case Study of Students' and Teachers' Perceptions in Finnish High School during the COVID Pandemic. *International Journal in Science and Technology in Education and Science*, 4 (4), 352-369.
- Ozmantar, M. F., & Agac, G. (2021). Mathematics teacher educators' knowledge sources in teacher education practices. *Mathematics Education Research Journal*, 35(1), 175-201. doi:10.1007/s13394-021-00382-x.
- Ozudogru, G. (2021). Problems faced in distance education during Covid-19 Pandemic. *Participatory Educational Research (PER)*, 321-333.
- Pastores, R., Dacanay, J., Mayoya, M., Nanglihan, M., & Bautista, R. (2021). "All by Myself with Mr. Google: The Pandemic Education from the Lenses of Secondary School Students." *American Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 9, no. 11, 660-664.
- Rasmitadila, Aliyyah, R., Rachmadtullah, R., Samsudin, A., Syaodih, E., Nurtanto, M., & Tambunan, A. (2020). The Perceptions of primary school teachers of online learning during the COVID-19 Pandemic period: A case study in Indonesia. *Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies*, 7(2), 90-109.
- Secundo, G., Gioconda, M. E., Del Vecchio, P., Gianluca, E., Margherita, A., & Valentina, N. (2021). Threat or opportunity? A case study of digital-enabled redesign of entrepreneurship education in the COVID-19 emergency. *Technological forecasting and social change*, 166.